

Conceptual Differences in Accounting for the Changes in the Ionic Sizes

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The effective ionic sizes of many ions were given and the different values for the same ion were attributed only to the low spin (LS) and high spin (HS) states associated with the ions¹.

Ion	Configuration	Size pm	Cjconfiguration	Size pm
Fe ^{II}	$t_{2g}^6 e_g^0$	75	$t_{2g}^4 e_g^2$	92
Fe ^{III}	$t_{2g}^5 e_g^0$	69	$t_{2g}^3 e_g^2$	78.5

The data¹ given in Table 1 implies that Fe^{II} has an ionic radius of 92 pm in the $t_{2g}^4 e_g^2$ configuration and 75 pm in the $t_{2g}^6 e_g^0$ configuration and so on. As a consequence of this it may lead to believe that in Fe^{II} the change in the spin state on its own can bring out a change in the ionic size by 17 pm and in Fe^{III} by 9.5 pm. Further arguments based on this, have crept into the text books also. For example¹ in the case of the hemoglobin molecule the size of Fe^{II} decreases on coordination with oxygen which then fits snugly in the porphyrin 'hole' and this has been attributed purely to the high-spin to low-spin transition, which is not completely true.

The change in the ionic size can not be attributed entirely to the change in the spin state only. The high-spin and low-spin radii of metal ions are taken from the complexes of the metal ions, with different ligands, which produce LS and HS states in the complexes. Under these conditions, one can not really compare and attribute the size difference

to the effects due to the spin states only. Rather the change can also be attributed to the interaction between the metal and ligands which is responsible for the different spin states, and subsequent partial transfer of electron density from the metal to the ligand which decreases the effective size of the ion.

In support of the above statement there were several reports confirming transfer of electron density from metal to ligand after complexation. It was proposed that in oxyhemoglobin one electron is transferred to oxygen from Fe^{II}^{2,3}, resulting in a low-spin complex of Fe^{III} with a super oxide anion radical (O_2^-). In this model HbO₂ and MbO₂ have two unpaired electrons, each one localised on the iron and the other on the oxygen. The diamagnetism results from the coupling of the unpaired spins on the adjacent atoms. Molecular orbital (MO) calculations⁴ and Mössbauer effect^{5,6} both indicate that electron density is transferred from iron to oxygen in HbO₂. The MO calculations suggest that 0.5 to 1.0 electronic charge units⁴ are transferred to oxygen, consistent with the formation of a super oxide.

The super oxide model has been questioned⁷ on the basis of the position of the superoxide ion in the spectrochemical series which suggests that a heme superoxide complex should be high-spin, i.e. HbO₂ should be high-spin. Furthermore, unsymmetrically bound O₂ and O_2^- should be observable in the infrared by an O-O stretching frequency. Since, no such ir absorption is observed,

it has been suggested⁷ that oxygen binding to hemoglobin involves the transfer of two electrons from the iron to oxygen resulting in a seven coordinate, Fe^{IV} complex with O₂²⁻. An analogous transfer of electrons from the metal to oxygen has been established by epr spectroscopy for the reversible binding of oxygen to various cobalt complexes^{8,9} including coboglobin¹⁰.

In hemoglobin¹¹ the Fe-O distance of 1.75 Å is about 0.1 Å shorter than expected from a summation of covalent radii and is also shorter than that observed (1.86 Å) in angular O₂ complexes of Co^{II}. This result clearly indicates significant multiple bonding. An explanation given by Hay¹² for the above observation is that coordinated singlet oxygen possibly experiences model *dπ-pπ* back-bonding from iron to O₂ with the transfer of electron density from the metal to oxygen.

All these reports suggest that there is a definite change in the electron density of the metal as a consequence of complexation which has a direct influence in deciding the effective size of the ion in addition to that due to the change in the spin state.

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